

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

Erlina Sih Rahayu¹, Erni Widiastuti², Sarsiti Sarsiti³, Juni Trisnowati⁴, Candra Setiawan⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Faculty of Economics, University of Surakarta, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research aims to determine the influence of work motivation and organizational culture on job satisfaction, the influence of work motivation, organizational culture and job satisfaction on employee performance as well as the influence of work motivation and organizational culture on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. This research is quantitative research, with a sampling technique using the Slovin formula. The population of this study was 102 employees, of which 50 employees were the research sample. The data analysis technique used is path analysis. The research results show that partially work motivation has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction and employee performance, however work motivation has an insignificant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable. Organizational culture partially has a positive and insignificant effect on job satisfaction and a significant negative effect on employee performance. Organizational culture has a significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

KEYWORDS: work motivation, organizational culture, employee performance, job satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Community Health Centers (Puskesmas) are part of the government agency that handles health implementation at the sub-district level. Puskesmas are established to provide basic, comprehensive, and integrated health services for all residents living in a specific work area. Puskesmas are the spearhead of health development, playing a significant role in achieving the seven health development goals. Puskesmas will be able to assess the performance of patient services through feedback provided by patients, which will then contribute to improving the performance of health workers in carrying out their duties. Puskesmas in Grogol Regency, Sukoharjo, play a significant role in achieving health development, influenced by the organization and management of personnel to carry out the main activities of the Puskesmas in this area.

Human resources in community health centers (Puskesmas) play a crucial role. Without the support of good human resources, the Puskesmas will face challenges in achieving its vision. Employees who perform well can support the achievement of the organization's goals. Employee performance is a crucial factor influencing the success or failure of an institution. The results of employee performance from 2022-2024 were rated Good for all employees. The following is the data on employee performance assessments at the Grogol Community Health Center in Sukoharjo Regency.

Table 1. Employee Performance Results based on assessment in E-KIN

Year	Assessment Items	Assessment Results
2022	Performance Result Rating	According to Expectations (100% of employees)
	Work Behavior Rating	According to Expectations (100% of employees)
	Periodic Performance Predicate	Good
2023	Performance Result Rating	According to Expectations (100% of employees)
	Work Behavior Rating	According to Expectations (100% of employees)
	Periodic Performance Predicate	Good
2024	Performance Result Rating	According to Expectations (100% of employees)
	TW I	Work Behavior Rating

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

Periodic Performance Predicate Good

Source: Secondary data, Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency 2024

There are several perspectives on the factors influencing employee performance, namely job satisfaction, work motivation, and organizational culture. Syah (2019:86) clarifies that job satisfaction is an attitudinal or emotional response to various aspects of work. Job satisfaction is a positive feeling regarding work tasks that is the result or achievement of an evaluation of their characteristics. The next factor indicated to influence employee performance is motivation. Motivation is a state that can drive employees to achieve goals. Work motivation is crucial for organizations because every organization seeks to achieve its goals. The higher the work motivation achieved by employees, the better their performance will be, as stated (Dewi et al., 2021). Work motivation not only influences individual productivity but also supports higher employee retention and job satisfaction (Liu & Batt, 2020). Furthermore, research by Jenkins and Delbridge (2021) indicates that work motivation not only strengthens productivity but also increases job satisfaction and employee retention. "Employee intrinsic motivation is closely related to increased productivity and higher retention" (Liu & Batt, 2020) in Rahayu and Widiasttuti (2024)

The next factor that can influence employee performance is organizational culture. Culture is a valuable asset for a company. The right corporate culture is believed to have the ability to direct the behavior of all organizational members toward desired goals. Every organization has a unique culture.

Based on the Goal-Setting Theory approach, employee success in managing an agency and achieving its targets, variables such as work motivation and organizational culture are the determining factors. The higher these determining factors, the greater the potential for success in achieving targets and goals (Dhermawan, et al. 2012). Based on the problem description above, this research was conducted to examine more deeply the relationship and influence of motivation and Organizational Culture on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable at the Grogol Sukoharjo Regency Health Center.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resource Management

Human resource management (HRM) is the process of managing and developing human resources within an organization (Lestari et al., 2023). Human resource management is concerned with utilizing human resources to achieve maximum effectiveness and efficiency in achieving company goals (Adipati, 2023).

Employee Performance

Performance is a well-known term in management, defined as work results, work achievements, and performance (Bagaskara et al., 2024). People will perform their best on a task if they have the will and desire to do it well.

Employee performance is the result of a process or activity within a specific function. This result represents the degree to which an employee completes work according to predetermined requirements (Fahmi & Mathori, 2023). Indicators used to measure employee performance variables include work quantity, punctuality, initiative, ability, and communication.

Job satisfaction

Suristya & Adi (2021) define job satisfaction as an employee's emotional state, whether or not there is a meeting point between the employee's work rewards and the company or organization's desired level of rewards. According to Melowdies & FoEh (2024), job satisfaction is an attitudinal or emotional response to various aspects of work.

Job satisfaction can also be defined as a positive or pleasant emotional expression resulting from an assessment of a job or work experience (Fitriadi et al., 2022). Indicators used to measure job satisfaction include the work itself, quality of supervision, relationships with coworkers, promotion opportunities, and pay.

Work motivation

Motivation is a mental state that drives a person, which in turn directs and channels behavior and actions, ultimately linked to the achievement of goals, whether personal or individual (Dewi et al., 2021). According to Laili & Safrizal (2021), work motivation is crucial for organizations because every organization seeks to achieve its goals. To achieve this, human involvement is essential. For employees to work in accordance with organizational goals, certain elements must be built within the organization.

(Putra, 2021) Motivation is defined as the drive or desire a person possesses to do something, to explore their potential, and to work toward achieving both individual and organizational goals. Motivation is created through the organization's role in addressing employee needs so they can work within the organization to achieve goals.

The indicators used to measure motivational variables are physical needs, the need for supporting facilities that can be

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

obtained in the workplace, the need for security, social needs, the need for appreciation, the need for appreciation for what someone has achieved, and the need for encouragement to achieve goals.

Organizational Culture

According to Wahyudi & Tupti (2019), organizational culture is a characteristic that exists within an organization and serves as a guideline for that organization, distinguishing it from other organizations. Organizational culture then becomes the organization's primary identity or character that is maintained and preserved (Deccasari, 2019).

(Sutoro et al., 2020) state that organizational culture, often known as work culture, is a set of organizational values that must be adhered to. The indicators used to measure organizational culture variables are integrity, consistency, professionalism, responsibility, and communication.

Previous Research

Previous studies relevant to this study include research conducted by (Hastuti, 2018) entitled "The Influence of Motivation, Competence and Satisfaction on the Performance of Health Cadres with Work Commitment as an Intervening Variable (Study of Pagiyanen Health Center, Tegal Regency)", which provides results that motivation, competence and commitment influence the performance of health cadres, Motivation and satisfaction variables influence the work commitment of health cadres. The conclusion is that there is no influence of motivation, competence and satisfaction on the performance of health cadres with work commitment as an intervening variable (Study of Pagiyanen Health Center, Tegal Regency).

Research (Jufrizen & Sitorus, 2021) entitled "The Effect of Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction on Performance with Work Discipline as an Intervening Variable" states that both work motivation and job satisfaction have an influence on work discipline and performance. Work discipline is able to mediate job satisfaction on performance, but is unable to mediate motivation on performance. Research from (Dewi et al., 2021) entitled "The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at the Denpasar City Social Service" also states that if work motivation and job satisfaction increase, employee performance will also increase. In addition, work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable, indicating that increasing work motivation, which is intervened by increasing job satisfaction, will improve employee performance at the Denpasar City Social Service. Laili & Safrizal (2021) conducted a study entitled The Influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Pulorejo Health Center. The results of the study indicate (1) Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, (2) Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. (3) Job Satisfaction has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance. (4) The indirect effect between work motivation on employee performance through job satisfaction is positive and insignificant.

Research by (Haryani et al., 2022) conducted a study entitled "Leadership, Organizational Culture and work motivation on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable". The results of the study indicate that leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, Organizational Culture has a positive but not significant effect on job satisfaction, work motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, organizational culture has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance, work motivation has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance, leadership has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction, organizational culture has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction, work motivation has a positive but significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction.

Research by (Bagaskara et al., 2024) entitled The Influence of Competence and Work Environment on Employee Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Case Study at UPT Puskesmas Babulu), which provides results that competence and work environment have a significant influence on performance either directly or mediated by job satisfaction. High employee competence and supported by a good work environment will increase employee job satisfaction which will then improve their performance. Research conducted by (Yuditia et al., 2023) with the title The Influence of Work Environment and Organizational Culture on Performance with Motivation as a Mediating Variable, provides results (1) Employee performance is significantly influenced by the work environment in the organization. (2) Organizational performance is directly influenced by the existing organizational culture. (3) Employee work motivation is greatly influenced by the work environment, and this has a direct impact on their performance. (4) Work motivation has a direct and significant influence on organizational culture and employee performance.

Research from (Haryadi & Wahyudi, 2020) entitled The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable, obtained the results (1) organizational culture has a significant positive effect

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

on employee performance, (2) organizational culture has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction, (3) organizational culture has a significant positive effect on employee performance through job satisfaction. Research by (Deccasari, 2019) entitled The Influence of Organizational Culture and Motivation on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Case Study at PT. Karya Mekar Dewatamali in Jombang City). The results of this study show (1) organizational culture organization has a significant influence on employee performance, (2) motivation has a significant influence on employee performance, (3) job satisfaction has a significant influence on employee performance, (4) organizational culture has a significant influence on job satisfaction, (5) motivation has a significant influence on job satisfaction, (6) organizational culture and motivation have a significant influence on employee performance with job satisfaction.

Hypothesis

The hypotheses proposed in this study are as follows:

1. H₁: Motivation has a significant positive effect on employee performance.
2. H₂: Organizational Culture has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance
3. H₃: Job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on employee performance.
4. H₄: Motivation has a significant positive effect on Job Satisfaction
5. H₅: Organizational Culture has a significant positive effect on Job Satisfaction
6. H₆: Motivation has a significant positive effect on employee performance with job Satisfaction work as an intervening variable
7. H₇: Organizational Culture has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an intervening variable

RESEARCH METHODS

This research method is a quantitative method using primary data. The population in this study were all employees of the Grogol Sukoharjo Community Health Center, totaling 102 employees. Sampling was carried out using the Random Sampling Method. In this study, the sample was calculated using the Slovin formula with a tolerable error rate of 10%, resulting in a sample of 50 respondents. The measurement of variables used in this study used a questionnaire with a Likert scale. The data analysis technique in this study used path analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Instrument Test

1. Validity test

Table 2. Validity test results

Variables	Statement	r count	r table	Information
Motivation (X ₁)	X _{1.1}	0.739	0.2787	Valid
	X _{1.2}	0.665		Valid
	X _{1.3}	0.625		Valid
	X _{1.4}	0.649		Valid
	X _{1.5}	0.675		Valid
Organizational Culture (X ₂)	X _{2.1}	0.685	0.2787	Valid
	X _{2.2}	0.780		Valid
	X _{2.3}	0.789		Valid
	X _{2.4}	0.794		Valid
	X _{2.5}	0.692		Valid
Satisfaction Work (Z)	Z ₋₁	0.553	0.2787	Valid
	Z ₋₂	0.702		Valid
	Z ₋₃	0.678		Valid
	Z ₋₄	0.580		Valid
	Z ₋₅	0.620		Valid
Performance Employee (Y)	Y ₋₁	0.601	0.2787	Valid
	Y ₋₂	0.708		Valid
	Y ₋₃	0.894		Valid
	Y ₋₄	0.823		Valid
	Y ₋₅	0.754		Valid

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

Based on the table above, it can be seen that all statement items for each variable have a calculated r value that is greater than the table r, so that all statement items are said to be valid.

2. Reliability test

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

Variables	Cronbach Alpha	Nunnally	Information
Motivation (X ₁)	0.688	0.60	Reliable
Organizational Culture (X ₂)	0.801	0.60	Reliable
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.617	0.60	Reliable
Employee Performance (Y)	0.798	0.60	Reliable

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Table 3 shows that the Cronbach's Alpha is greater than 0.60. This indicates that all statements in this research questionnaire are reliable and can be used in subsequent research analyses.

DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

1. Classical Assumption Test

a. Normality Test

Table 4. Results of the Normality Test for Equation I

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
Unstandardized Residual		
N		50
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Standard Deviation	2.08036062
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.086
	Positive	.070
	Negative	-.086
Test Statistics		.086
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the Asymp.Sig value is 0.200 > 0.05, so it can be confirmed that the data is normally distributed.

Table 5. Results of the Normality Test for Equation II

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
Unstandardized Residual		
N		50
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Standard Deviation	1.54294636
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.102
	Positive	.066
	Negative	-.102
Test Statistics		.102
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the Asymp.Sig value is 0.200 > 0.05, so it can be confirmed that the data is normally distributed.

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

b. Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 6. Results of Heteroscedasticity Test for Equation I

Coefficientsa						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	3,417	1,605		2,130	.038
	Motivation	-.026	.100	-.050	-.255	.800
	Culture Organization	-.073	.080	-.178	-.909	.368
a. Dependent Variable: ABS_RES1						

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the table above, the significance value of the independent variable Motivation is $0.800 > 0.05$, Organizational Culture $0.368 > 0.05$, which means that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Table 7. Results of Heteroscedasticity Test for Equation II

Coefficientsa						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	4,490	1,279		3,511	.001
	Motivation	-.022	.073	-.132	-1,762	.080
	Culture Organization	.057	.057	.189	1,003	.321
	Job satisfaction	-.004	.065	-.010	-.058	.954
a. Dependent Variable: ABS_RES2						

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

From the table above, it is known that the significance value of the Motivation variable is $0.080 > 0.05$, Organizational Culture $0.321 > 0.05$, and Job Satisfaction $0.954 > 0.05$, which means that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

c. Multicollinearity Test

Table 8. Results of Multicollinearity Test for Equation I

Coefficientsa								
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Collinearity Statistics		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	9,702	2,486		3,903	.000		
	Motivation	.352	.155	.365	2,264	.028	.531	1,884
	Culture Organization	.213	.124	.278	1,722	.092	.531	1,884
a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction								

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test, the overall tolerance value is greater than 0.10 and the VIF is less than 10, so it can be seen that the data does not have multicollinearity.

Table 9. Results of Multicollinearity Test for Equation II

Coefficientsa							
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Collinearity Statistics	

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	4,032	2,536		1,590	.119		
Motivation	.150	.145	.146	1,035	.306	.479	2,089
Organizational culture	-.091	.113	-.111	-.802	.427	.499	2,003
Job satisfaction	.768	.129	.719	5,939	.000	.650	1,539
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance							

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test, the overall tolerance value is greater than 0.10 and the VIF is less than 10, so it can be seen that the data does not have multicollinearity.

2. Hypothesis Testing

a. Partial t-test

Table 10. Results of the t-test of equation I

Coefficients ^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	9,702	2,486		3,903	.000
	Motivation	.352	.155	.365	2,264	.028
	Organizational culture	.213	.124	.278	1,722	.092
a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction						

Source: Processed primary data, 2024 Based on the results of the t-test, it can be seen that:

- 1) The motivation variable (X_1) obtained a significance value of $0.028 < 0.05$ and a positive coefficient, so in other words, motivation (X_1) partially has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction (Z). H_1 is accepted.
- 2) The organizational culture variable (X_2) obtained a significance value of $0.092 > 0.05$ and a positive coefficient, so in other words, organizational culture (X_2) partially has a positive but insignificant effect on job satisfaction (Z). H_2 is accepted.

Table 11. Results of the t-test of equation II

Coefficients ^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	4,030	2,260		1,783	.081
	Motivation	.324	.127	.316	2,560	.014
	Organizational culture	-.336	.094	-.425	-3,567	.001
	Job satisfaction	.836	.115	.783	7,284	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee

Source: Processed primary data, 2024 Based on the results of the t-test, it can be seen that:

- 1) The motivation variable (X_1) obtained a significance value of $0.014 < 0.05$ and a positive coefficient, so in other words, motivation (X_1) partially has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y). H_3 is accepted.
- 2) The organizational culture variable (X_2) obtained a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$ and a negative coefficient, so in other words, organizational culture (X_2) partially has a significant negative effect on employee performance (Y). H_4 is accepted.
- 3) The job satisfaction variable (Z) obtained a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a positive coefficient, so in other words, job satisfaction (Z) partially has a significant positive effect on employee performance (Y). H_5 is accepted.

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

b. Path Analysis

Table 12. Results of Path Analysis of Model I

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.592a	.350	.322	1,796
a. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Culture, Motivation				

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

It is known that the R Square value is 0.350, which means that the contribution of the influence of the Motivation and Organizational Culture variables on Job Satisfaction is 35.0%, the remaining 65% is explained by variations in other variables outside this study.

$$\text{Value } e_1 = 1 - 0.350$$

$$= 0.806225775$$

$$Z = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$= 9.702 + 0.365 X_1 + 0.278 X_2 + 0.806$$

Table 13. Results of Path Analysis of Equation II

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.807a	.652	.629	1,419
a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction, Organizational Culture, Motivation				

Source: Primary data processed by SPSS. 2024

It is known that the R Square value is 0.652, which means that the contribution of the influence of the variables Motivation, Organizational Culture and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance is 65.2%, the remaining 34.8% is explained by variations in other variables outside this study.

$$\text{Value of } e_1 = 1 - 0.652$$

$$= 0.589915248$$

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 Z + e$$

$$= 4.030 + 0.316 X_1 - 0.425 X_2 + 0.783 Z + 0.590$$

Based on the data results, it can be seen that there are direct influences, indirect influences and total influences from this research, namely;

- 1) Direct influence of Motivation (X1) on Job Satisfaction (Z) (P1) = 0.365
- 2) Direct influence of Motivation (X1) on Employee Performance (Y) (P3) = 0.316
- 3) The indirect effect of motivation (X1) on employee performance (Y) through job satisfaction (Z) (P6) = 0.365 x 0.783 = 0.286, meaning that the indirect effect is smaller than the direct effect, so H₆ is rejected.
- 4) Effect of Job Satisfaction (Z) on Employee Performance (Y) (P5) = 0.783
- 5) Direct influence of Organizational Culture (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Z) (P2) = 0.278
- 6) Direct influence of Organizational Culture (X2) on Employee Performance (Y) (P4) = - 0.425
- 7) The indirect influence of Organizational Culture (X2) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z) (P7) = 0.278 x 0.783 = 0.218, meaning that the indirect influence is greater than the direct influence, so H₇ is accepted.

DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Motivation (X₁) on Job Satisfaction (Z)

Partial testing of motivation (X₁) on job satisfaction (Z) can be seen a significance value of 0.028 < 0.05 and a positive coefficient, in other words the results of the statistical test indicate that motivation at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency partially has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction (Z). Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that work motivation at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency has a positive and significant effect on job

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

satisfaction. This shows that the higher the work motivation of employees, the higher the job satisfaction they feel. This finding supports the view of Robbins and Judge (2017) who stated that motivation is one of the important determinants that can increase job satisfaction through intrinsic and extrinsic encouragement.

Theoretically, the results of this study align with Herzberg's two-factor theory, in which motivating factors such as achievement, recognition, responsibility, and opportunities for self-development play a significant role in increasing employee job satisfaction. Similarly, Maslow's theory of needs states that fulfilling human needs, from physiological to self-actualization, will increase individual job satisfaction. Motivation provided through leadership support, rewards, a comfortable work environment, and opportunities for competency development have been shown to increase employee job satisfaction. This is consistent with research conducted by Luthans (2011), which states that high motivation will create a more conducive work environment and have a direct impact on job satisfaction.

Furthermore, the results of this study also show that motivation acts as an intervening variable that can strengthen the relationship between organizational factors and employee job satisfaction. Thus, motivation is not only a driving factor for performance but also a crucial bridge that mediates the influence of the work environment on job satisfaction. Practically, these findings provide implications for the management of the Grogol Community Health Center to continuously improve employee motivation through appropriate managerial strategies, such as providing rewards, providing adequate work facilities, and creating a positive work climate. This is in line with research conducted by Sutanto and Ratnawati (2019), which found that work motivation has a significant influence on job satisfaction in public sector organizations in Indonesia.

Thus, it can be concluded that work motivation at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency, has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, while strengthening its role as an intervening variable that contributes to increasing organizational work effectiveness. The results of this study indicate that the first hypothesis (H_1) is accepted, namely that motivation has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. This is in line with the results of research conducted by (Laili & Safrizal, 2021) and (Dewi et al., 2021).

2. The Influence of Organizational Culture (X_2) on Job Satisfaction (Z)

Partial testing of organizational culture (X_2) on job satisfaction (Z) can be seen a significance value of $0.092 > 0.05$ and a positive coefficient, in other words the results of the statistical test indicate that organizational culture at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency partially has a positive but insignificant effect on job satisfaction (Z). Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that organizational culture at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency partially has a positive but insignificant effect on job satisfaction. This shows that although a good organizational culture can contribute to increasing job satisfaction, its influence is not strong or consistent enough to explain variations in employee job satisfaction.

Theoretically, these results can be explained by the perspective of Robbins and Judge (2017), who stated that organizational culture is a system of shared meanings held by organizational members and serves as a guide for action. A strong culture can influence employee behavior and create a more harmonious work environment. However, in some cases, the influence of organizational culture on job satisfaction is not always significant, especially if other factors such as motivation, rewards, or working conditions are more dominant in shaping employee satisfaction. This finding is also in line with research conducted by Schein (2010), which emphasized that organizational culture does play a role in directing employee behavior, but its level of significance on job satisfaction depends on the organizational context, leadership style, and managerial system implemented. In other words, at the Grogol Community Health Center, organizational culture may not have been fully embedded consistently or not yet strongly felt by all employees, so its impact on job satisfaction is not significant.

However, the direction of the influence of organizational culture remains positive, meaning that the better the organizational culture created, the greater the chance of increasing employee job satisfaction, although this was not proven to be significant in this study. This indicates that organizational culture can still function as an intervening variable, although its contribution is relatively small compared to other factors such as motivation. The practical implication of this finding is that the management of the Grogol Community Health Center needs to strengthen the implementation of a consistent organizational culture, for example through internalizing work values, improving communication between employees, and enforcing fair discipline. These steps are expected to strengthen the influence of organizational culture so that it can have a more significant impact on job satisfaction in the future.

Thus, it can be concluded that organizational culture at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency, has a positive but insignificant effect on job satisfaction. Although its role as an intervening variable is relatively weak, organizational culture still contributes to supporting the effectiveness of organizational performance. The results of this study indicate that the second hypothesis (H_2) is rejected, namely that organizational culture has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. This is in

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

line with the results of research conducted by (Wastuti & Widiastuti, 2021) and (Haryani et al., 2022) but not in line with research by (Deccasari, 2019).

3. The Influence of Motivation (X_1) on Employee Performance (Y)

Partial testing of motivation (X_1) on employee performance (Y) can be seen a significance value of $0.014 < 0.05$ and a positive coefficient, in other words the results of the statistical test indicate that motivation at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency partially has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y). Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that work motivation at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency partially has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This shows that the higher the motivation of employees, the higher the performance produced. In other words, motivation is an important factor that encourages employees to work more optimally, complete tasks well, and provide quality health services to the community.

These findings are consistent with Robbins and Judge's (2017) opinion, which states that motivation is an individual's willingness to exert high levels of effort toward achieving organizational goals, which is influenced by the ability of those efforts to meet individual needs. High motivation will encourage employees to achieve established performance standards. Furthermore, the results of this study also prove that job satisfaction acts as an intervening variable that strengthens the relationship between motivation and employee performance. This means that motivation not only directly impacts performance but also indirectly improves performance through increased job satisfaction. Herzberg's (1966) Two Factor Theory supports these findings, where motivating factors such as recognition, achievement, and self-development not only increase job satisfaction but also have implications for improving employee performance.

Motivation reflected through leadership support, reward systems, competency development opportunities, and a conducive work environment has been shown to increase job satisfaction. Satisfied employees tend to perform better because they feel valued, supported, and have room to grow. This aligns with research conducted by Luthans (2011), which states that motivation is a key determinant in achieving organizational performance through increased employee job satisfaction. Furthermore, research by Sutanto and Ratnawati (2019) also shows that work motivation significantly influences performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable in the public sector in Indonesia. These findings reinforce the point that in public service organizations such as Community Health Centers (Puskesmas), increasing employee motivation is a crucial strategy for improving both job satisfaction and service performance to the public.

Thus, it can be concluded that work motivation at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency, has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, both directly and indirectly through job satisfaction as an intervening variable. This emphasizes the importance of Community Health Center management in designing strategies to increase employee motivation in order to achieve more effective organizational performance. The third hypothesis (H_3) in this study is accepted, namely that motivation has a significant positive effect on employee performance. This is in line with the results of research conducted by Hastuti (2018) and Dewi et al. (2021), but not in line with the results of research by Haryani et al. (2022).

4. The Influence of Organizational Culture (X_2) on Employee Performance (Y)

Partial testing of organizational culture (X_2) on employee performance (Y) can be seen a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$ and a negative coefficient, in other words the results of the statistical test indicate that organizational culture at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency partially has a significant negative effect on employee performance (Y). Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that organizational culture at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency partially has a negative and significant effect on employee performance. This means that the existing organizational culture has not been able to support the improvement of employee performance, even tends to reduce work effectiveness. In other words, although organizational culture is usually expected to provide direction, values, and guidelines in work, in this context the organizational culture implemented at the Grogol Community Health Center may not be in accordance with employee needs, thus having a negative impact on performance.

Theoretically, Robbins and Judge (2017) state that organizational culture is a system of shared meanings held by members of an organization. If the culture is too rigid, non-adaptive, or does not provide enough room for innovation, it can lead to resistance, conflict, and decreased work motivation, ultimately resulting in decreased performance. Furthermore, Schein (2010) emphasized that organizational culture can be a powerful force in shaping employee behavior. However, if cultural values are not aligned with employee needs and the demands of the work environment, the culture can become an obstacle to achieving organizational goals. This may explain why organizational culture at the Grogol Community Health Center actually has a significant negative impact on performance.

Furthermore, the results of this study also indicate that job satisfaction acts as an intervening variable in the relationship

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

between organizational culture and employee performance. An inappropriate organizational culture can decrease job satisfaction, which in turn impacts employee performance. This finding aligns with the results of research conducted by Sutanto and Ratnawati (2019), which stated that organizational culture has a significant influence on job satisfaction and performance, both positively and negatively, depending on how the culture is implemented in public organizations. Indications of an unsupportive organizational culture can include ineffective communication, inconsistent value implementation, or a misalignment between management policies and employee needs. These factors can decrease job satisfaction, which ultimately has implications for declining health service performance.

Thus, it can be concluded that organizational culture at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency, has a negative and significant effect on employee performance, both directly and through job satisfaction as an intervening variable. This finding provides important implications: Puskesmas management needs to evaluate and improve organizational culture to make it more adaptive, participatory, and aligned with employee needs and healthcare service demands. The results of this study reject the fourth hypothesis (H_4), which states that organizational culture has a significant negative effect on employee performance. This finding aligns with the results of research conducted by (Nadhiroh et al., 2022) but not with research by (Haryadi & Wahyudi, 2020).

5. The Effect of Job Satisfaction (Z) on Employee Performance (Y)

Partial testing of job satisfaction (Z) on employee performance (Y) can be seen a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a positive coefficient, in other words the results of the statistical test indicate that job satisfaction at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency partially has a significant positive effect on employee performance (Y). The results of the study indicate that job satisfaction at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency partially has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This means that the higher the level of job satisfaction felt by employees, the better the performance displayed in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Conversely, employees who are dissatisfied tend to show declining performance.

These findings are consistent with Robbins and Judge's (2017) opinion, which states that job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude toward their work, and satisfied employees typically have higher motivation, stronger loyalty, and better work productivity. In other words, job satisfaction is a key determinant of employee performance improvement. Furthermore, the results of this study reinforce Herzberg's (1966) two-factor motivation theory, which states that job satisfaction is influenced by motivating factors such as achievement, recognition, responsibility, and self-development. When employees feel satisfied because these factors are met, they are motivated to work more optimally, thereby improving their performance.

Job satisfaction is reflected in a sense of comfort at work, good relationships between employees, appreciation from leaders, and opportunities for self-development. These conditions encourage employees to work with greater discipline, provide better service to the public, and achieve organizational targets. This finding aligns with research by Luthans (2011), which confirms that job satisfaction is closely linked to improved performance because satisfied employees tend to be more enthusiastic and focused on achieving organizational goals. Furthermore, research conducted by Sutanto and Ratnawati (2019) also demonstrated that job satisfaction acts as an intervening variable, strengthening the relationship between organizational factors (such as motivation and work culture) and the performance of public sector employees in Indonesia. This also occurred at the Grogol Community Health Center, where job satisfaction proved to be a crucial bridge connecting internal organizational factors with employee performance.

Thus, it can be concluded that job satisfaction at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency, has a positive and significant impact on employee performance, while strengthening its role as an intervening variable in improving organizational effectiveness. The results of this study indicate that the fifth hypothesis (H_5) is accepted, namely that job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on employee performance. This finding aligns with the results of research conducted by (Jufrizen & Sitorus, 2021) but is inconsistent with research by (Deccasari, 2019) and (Haryadi & Wahyudi, 2020).

6. The Influence of Motivation (X_1) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z)

The direct influence of Motivation (X_1) on Employee Performance Y (P_3) = 0.316, the direct influence of Motivation (X_1) on Job Satisfaction (Z) (P_1) = 0.365, the indirect influence of Motivation (X_1) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z) (P_6) = $0.365 \times 0.783 = 0.286$. Based on the results of the analysis and calculations, it is known that the direct influence is 0.316 and the indirect influence is 0.286, which means that the indirect influence is smaller than the direct influence so that indirectly motivation through job satisfaction does not have a significant influence on employee performance. The results of this study reject the sixth hypothesis (H_6)

Based on the analysis, it was found that motivation through job satisfaction did not have a significant impact on employee

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

performance at the Grogol Community Health Center in Sukoharjo Regency. This indicates that although motivation can increase employee job satisfaction, this increase in job satisfaction does not automatically lead to significant performance improvements. Theoretically, Robbins and Judge (2017) explain that motivation is closely related to job satisfaction and performance, but this relationship is not always linear. In some organizational conditions, employees who feel satisfied with their jobs do not necessarily show higher performance. This can occur if the satisfaction obtained is passive, for example, only feeling comfortable with the work environment, but not accompanied by encouragement to increase productivity.

This finding can also be explained through Herzberg's (1966) Two Factor Theory. Herzberg distinguished between motivating factors (achievement, recognition, advancement) that can increase job satisfaction, and hygiene factors (working conditions, relationships with superiors, salary) that only prevent dissatisfaction. If employee job satisfaction at the Grogol Community Health Center is largely shaped by hygiene factors, then even if satisfaction increases, it is not strong enough to drive improved performance. The results of this study differ from several previous studies that have shown the mediating influence of job satisfaction.

Thus, it can be concluded that motivation through job satisfaction does not indirectly significantly impact employee performance at the Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency. This finding implies that Community Health Center management needs to emphasize motivation-boosting strategies that directly impact performance, such as setting clear work targets, providing performance-based incentives, and continuous monitoring and evaluation. The results of this study align with those of (Laili & Safrizal, 2021) but differ from those of (Deccasari, 2019) and (Haryani et al., 2022).

7. The Influence of Organizational Culture (X_2) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z)

The direct influence of Organizational Culture (X_2) on Employee Performance Y (P_4) = - 0.425, The direct influence of Organizational Culture (X_2) on Job Satisfaction (Z) (P_2) = 0.278, The indirect influence of Organizational Culture (X_2) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z) (P_7) = $0.278 \times 0.783 = 0.218$. Based on the results of the analysis and calculations, it is known that the direct influence is - 0.425 and the indirect influence is 0.218, which means that the indirect influence is greater than the direct influence so that indirectly organizational culture through job satisfaction has a significant influence on employee performance. The results of this study indicate that the seventh hypothesis (H_7) is accepted

Based on the analysis, it was found that the indirect influence of organizational culture on employee performance through job satisfaction is greater than its direct influence. This means that organizational culture not only plays a direct role in improving performance but is more effective when working through increasing employee job satisfaction at the Grogol Community Health Center in Sukoharjo Regency. In theory, Robbins and Judge (2017) explain that organizational culture shapes values, norms, and beliefs that are internalized by employees. A positive culture will create a supportive work environment, thereby fostering job satisfaction. Ultimately, satisfied employees will be more motivated, have high loyalty, and are able to deliver optimal performance.

These findings align with Luthans' (2011) theory, which asserts that job satisfaction is an important psychological variable that can mediate the relationship between organizational factors and individual performance. If organizational culture only emphasizes formal rules or structures without creating comfort and a sense of belonging, its impact on performance can be limited. However, when organizational culture fosters job satisfaction, its influence on performance becomes stronger. The results of this study are consistent with the findings of Sutanto and Ratnawati (2019), who showed that organizational culture positively influences performance through job satisfaction in public sector organizations. Similarly, research by Putri and Taufiq (2020) found that job satisfaction can mediate the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance, so that the indirect effect is more dominant than the direct effect.

An organizational culture that emphasizes excellent service, teamwork, and open communication successfully increases employee job satisfaction. This satisfaction then drives increased intrinsic motivation, pride in work, and commitment to the organization. Thus, the indirect effect of organizational culture on performance through job satisfaction is stronger and more significant than its direct effect. These findings provide practical implications for the management of the Grogol Community Health Center, namely the importance of strengthening an organizational culture oriented towards employee satisfaction, for example by creating a conducive work environment, rewarding achievement, and opening up two-way communication. This strategy not only strengthens organizational culture but also ensures that it is truly perceived as a source of job satisfaction, thus positively impacting employee performance on an ongoing basis. The results of this study align with research by (Haryadi & Wahyudi, 2020) but are inconsistent with research by (Haryani et al., 2022).

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

The conclusion of this study entitled The Effect Of Work Motivation And Organizational Culture On Employee Performance With Job Satisfaction As An Intervening Variable At The Grogol Community Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency is as follows :

1. Motivation has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction
2. Organizational culture has a positive but insignificant effect on job satisfaction
3. Motivation has a significant positive effect on employee performance
4. Organizational culture has a significant negative effect on employee performance
5. Job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on employee performance
6. Motivation has no significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.
7. Organizational culture has a significant influence on employee performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

SUGGESTION

The suggestions in this research are as follows:

1. For the Management of Puskesmas Grogol, Sukoharjo Regency

The management is expected to enhance an organizational culture that supports job satisfaction, for example by strengthening internal communication, creating a conducive work environment, and providing appreciation for employee achievements. These efforts are believed to encourage optimal improvement in employee performance.

2. For the Employees of Puskesmas Grogol, Sukoharjo Regency

Employees are advised to continuously improve their intrinsic motivation, such as service spirit, sense of responsibility, and professionalism. In addition, it is important to maintain job satisfaction through teamwork and openness. Thus, employees' contribution to achieving organizational goals can be more maximized.

3. For Future Researchers

Future studies are recommended to add other variables, such as leadership, compensation, or organizational commitment, as well as to broaden the research object to other public health centers or different public service institutions. This is expected to enrich empirical findings and provide a more comprehensive overview of the factors influencing employee performance.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adipati, D. (2023). The Influence of Knowledge, Ability, and Work Experience on Employee Performance at PT. Pelindo IV Makassar.
- 2) Almasri, MN (2016). Human Resource Management: Implementation in Islamic Education. *Kutubkhanah: Journal of Social and Religious Research*, 19(2), 133–151.
- 3) Bagaskara, D., Wulur, FC, Nurdin, A., Auliyani, W., & Sikki, N. (2024). The Influence of Competence and Work Environment on Employee Performance with Employee Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Case Study at the Babulu Community Health Center). *Journal of Innovation Research Management (MRI)*, 2(2), 41–52. <https://doi.org/10.55606/jimas.v2i2.2472>.
- 4) Deccasari, DD (2019). The Influence of Organizational Culture and Motivation on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Case Study at PT. Karya Mekar Dewatamali in Jombang City). *Journal of Business & Management Accounting*, 25(1), 43-55.
- 5) Dewi, NPC, Wimba, IGA, & Agustina, MDP (2021). The Influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at the Denpasar City Social Service. *Widya Amrita: Journal of Management, Entrepreneurship and Tourism*, 1(4), 1240–1252.
- 6) Firmansyah, NA, & Maria, V. (2022). The Influence of Leadership, Organizational Culture, and Work Motivation on Employee Performance at PT. The Univenus Serang. *Journal of Research Innovation*, 2(12), 3841–3848.
- 7) Fitriadi, Y., Susanto, R., Irdam, & Wahyuni, R. (2022). The Contribution of Job Engagement to Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction. *Jurnal Ekobistek*, 11(4), 448–453. <https://doi.org/10.35134/ekobistek.v11i4.446>.
- 8) Haryadi, D., & Wahyudi, W. (2020). The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. *Journal of Management and Business Strategy*, 1(1), 15-21.
- 9) Haryani, T., Kirana, KC, & Wiyono, G. (2022). Leadership, Organizational Culture, and Work Motivation on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. *TheJournalish: Social and Government*, 3(1), 55–74. <http://thejournalish.com/ojs/index.php/thejournalish/index>

The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Grogol Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency

- 10) Hasica, MI, Isyanto, P., & Yani, D. (2023). The Influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance at the Karawang Regency DPRD Secretariat. *Economina Journal*, 2(7), 1535–1545. <https://doi.org/10.55681/economina.v2i7.625>
- 11) Hastuti, D. (2018). The Influence of Motivation, Competence, and Satisfaction on Health Cadres with Work Commitment as an Intervening Variable (Study of Pagiyanen Community Health Center, Tegal Regency). *Magisma Journal*, 6(1), 23–34.
- 12) Hidayat, R., & Anwar, SA (2023). Human Resource Management (Case Study: Qurrota A'yun Islamic Education College). *JSTAF: Siddiq, Tabligh, Amanah, Fathonah*, 2(2), 392–401. <https://doi.org/10.62515/staf>
- 13) Hutagalung, BA (2022). Analysis of Factors Influencing Employee Performance: Competence, Motivation, and Work Environment (Human Resource Management Literature Review). *JMPIS: Journal of Educational Management and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 201–210. <https://doi.org/10.38035/jmpis.v3i1>
- 14) Jufrizen, & Sitorus, ST (2021). The Influence of Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction on Performance with Work Discipline as an Intervening Variable. *SiNTESa CERED National Seminar on Educational Technology and Humanities*, 841–856.
- 15) Karuniawati, SDJ, Halim, A., & Farhan, D. (2022). The Effect of Training and Non-Physical Work Environment on Performance Mediated by Work Motivation. *Management and Economics Journal (MEC-J)*, 6(1), 81-90.
- 16) Kreitner, R., & Kinicki, A. (2014). *Organizational Behavior* (10th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- 17) Kristin, H. (2021). The Influence of Work Environment and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at PT. Eka Warna Kimia.
- 18) Laili, RR, & Safrizal, HB (2021). The Influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at Pulorejo Community Health Center. *Journal of Management Science Studies*, 1(3), 225–231. <https://journal.trunojoyo.ac.id/jkim>
- 19) Lestari, S., Syahriza, R., & Harahap, MI (2023). Human resource management strategies in improving employee performance quality. *Innovation: Journal of Economics, Finance and Management*, 19(3), 720–729.
- 20) Luthans, F. (2011). *Organizational Behavior: An Evidence-Based Approach* (12th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- 21) Nadhiroh, U., Saptaria, L., & Ambarwati, D. (2022). The Influence of Motivation, Supervision, and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Work Environment as a Moderating Variable at PT. Nabatex, Mojo District, Kediri Regency. *SEIKO: Journal of Management & Business*: 4(3), 517-527.
- 22) Ningsih, S. (2022). The Influence of Organizational Culture, Organizational Commitment, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at PT. Capella Dinamik Nusantara, Kandis District, Siak Regency, Riau Province.
- 23) Putra, OJ (2021). The Influence of Motivation and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment as an Intervening Variable.
- 24) Putri, PA (2023). The Influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance at PT. Pegadaian (Persero) Bogor Branch.
- 25) Putri, AN, & Taufiq, M. (2020). The Role of Job Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable in the Relationship between Organizational Culture and Employee Performance. *Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship*, 22(1), 15–26. <https://doi.org/10.9744/jmk.22.1.15-26>
- 26) Rahayu, Erlina Sih & Widiastuti, Erni (2024). Analysis of the Influence of Transformational Leadership, Training and Development, and Work Motivation on Employee Performance at PT. BPR BKK JATENG (PESERODA) Karanganyar Branch. *Jurnal Edunomika –Vol. 08, No. 02, 2024.*
- 27) Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2017). *Organizational Behavior* (17th ed.). Boston: Pearson.
- 28) Saripuddin. (2021). The Influence of Organizational Culture, Organizational Communication, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Bantimurung District Office, Maros Regency.
- 29) Schein, E. H. (2010). *Organizational Culture and Leadership* (4th ed.). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- 30) Sutanto, EM, & Ratnawati, V. (2019). The Influence of Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction of Public Sector Employees in Indonesia. *Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship*, 21(2), 101–110. <https://doi.org/10.9744/jmk.21.2.101-110>
- 31) Sutoro, M., Mawardi, S., & Sugiarti, E. (2020). The Influence of Leadership, Compensation, Organizational Culture, and Job Satisfaction on Civil Servant Performance. *Scientific Journal of Reflection: Economic, Accounting, Management and Business*, 3(4), 411–420.
- 32) Wastuti, E., Dwi., & Widiastuti, E. (2021). The Influence of Organizational Culture, Leadership Style and Work Environment on Employee Job Satisfaction at PT. Columbus Sarana Mandiri Solo. *Journal of Research and Scientific Studies*, 19(1), 44-50.
- 33) Yudhy, Y., & Nur'aeni, N. (2020). The Influence of Organization Culture and Work Motivation on Employee Productivity of Bank BJB Rancaekek Branch. *International Journal of Business, Economics, and Social Development*, 1(4), 202-211.